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Jurisprudential Thoughts And Perspectives From Theories Of Social Contract, Utilitarianism And Humanism On The Concept Of Right To Die

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ABSTRACT

The concept of the right to die which is one of the most controversial aspects amongst other rights of an individual and limitation placed on such rights by the state authorities as discussed under the social contract theory has received crucial attention in the medico-legal field. Using doctrinal method, this article examined this concept under three jurisprudential theories in order to bring out a clearer understanding. Through jurisprudential perspectives from humanism and utilitarianism, justifications for vesting the right to die in a patient who is experiencing excruciating pains were identified. It was recommended that patient who is terminally ill and experiencing excruciating pain should be accorded right to die voluntarily, especially if such person has attained the age of majority and a specific law should be put in place to protect the rights of such patient. This work concluded that this will bring the position of the law in Nigeria in line with best medical and acceptable practices in other jurisdictions, in order to enable doctors to act in the best interests of their patients without any form of fear of prosecution or the need to dissemble.

Keywords: Right To Die, Theories, Social Contract, Humanism, Utilitarianism

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Understanding the concept of right to die which has generated a lot of bioethical and biomedical controversies even in clinical situations¹, signifies the bringing about a painless and peaceful death, especially in respect of those suffering from painful and incurable disease.² The case of the right to die is usually made for the patients with the terminally ill diseases, bedridden in hospitals, living in a persistent vegetative state and those who are unconscious without the hope of recovery requesting for peaceful and painless death.³ The concept of right to die involves the act or practice of killing or bringing about the death of a person who voluntarily requests for painless or peaceful death for reasons of mercy because he or she is suffering from an incurable disease or condition, particularly an excruciating pain. In essence,

¹ Rosangela Barcaro, 'The Right to Die Debate' (2001) 14(1) A Survey of Global Bioethics 85.

² H. Biggs, *Euthanasia: Death with Dignity and the law* (Oxford: Hart Publishing Ltd. 2001) 21

³ Ibid

the death mentioned herein will be easy and painless in order to produce a relief from a painful state of living.⁴

It is common for people to say that life is sacred but they do not mean that all life is sacred, therefore when people in the context of medical ethics, discuss the sanctity of life, they generally mean the intrinsic value and inviolability of human life, rather than all life, it is primarily applied to human beings, particularly in discussions about concept of right to die. It's important to note that the principle of the sanctity of life does not necessarily extend to all forms of life, such as animals, plants, or even non-human organisms.⁵

Flowing from above, fundamental questions arise whether the right to die can be said to be connected to the right to life? Apparently, emerging from the right to life is the concept of right to die.⁶ Then does voluntary death of a patient through the concept of the right to die constitute violation of the right to life? Why will the Constitution of a country that granted a person the right to life would deny or refuse such a person the right to die voluntarily? The constitution does not create life but only creates means of protecting it because God is regarded as the creator, author and giver of life⁷, therefore no one has neither the right to take life⁸ nor can waive his or her right to live. It was held in *R (Pretty) v DPP*⁹ that the right to life did not imply a right to die. It was explained in *Airedale NHS Trust v Bland*¹⁰ that when death occurred in the eyes of the medical world and of the law, a person is not clinically dead so long as the brain stem retains its function.¹¹ Flowing from this, is the controversial question whether a person experiencing excruciating pain and agony and has become the cause of suffering and anguish to himself and his loved ones, be denied the right to die? Therefore, request for peaceful and painless death is more pressing in the recent times as a result of the sophisticated technological practices in medicine such as live saving machines that can be used to prolong a patient's live beyond the natural period.¹²

Historically and for more than two decades, the Netherlands was the first country to give legal effect to the concept of right to die.¹³ The number of people who have been accorded the right to die has progressively increased year after year.¹⁴ A patient will be accorded the right to die only if the criteria outlined in the Dutch Termination of Life on Request and Assisted Suicide (Review Procedures) Act are strictly followed. Voluntary request for peaceful and painless death will be made by a patient who is suffering from unbearable pain and have no hope of recovery. Such patient regards right to die as the only way out of the dilemma.¹⁵ In the *Schooheim case*¹⁶ the Dutch Supreme Court ruled and relied on the principles, that both legal and medical rules require a free and explicit request from the patient.¹⁷ Several factors must be met before a right to die can be granted. The conditions are as follows: The patient must request for a peaceful and painless death, which must be free and voluntary; The patient's request must be well-considered, durable, and persistent; The patient must be experiencing intolerable (not necessarily physical) suffering with no prospect of improvement; peaceful and painless death must be a last resort

⁴ Y. Olomajobi, *Human rights and civil liberties in Nigeria* (Ikeja: Princeton Press Ltd, 2018) 32

⁵ Peter Singer, 'Unsanctifying Human Life: Essays On Ethics' In John Ladd, *Ethical Issues Relating To Life And Death* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1979) p. 214

⁶ Y. Olomajobi, *Human rights and civil liberties in Nigeria* (Ikeja: Princeton Press Ltd, 2018) 32

⁷ The Holy Bible, Genesis 2:7

⁸ The Holy Bible, Exodus 20:13; Deuteronomy 5:17

⁹ (2002) 1 AC 800

¹⁰ (1993) 1 ALL ER 831

¹¹ *Ibid* at 859

¹² Mike Obi, 'A Critical Appraisal Of Euthanasia Under Nigerian Laws' (2014) *Nnamidi Azikiwe University Journal of International Law and Jurisprudence* 75.

¹³ Termination of Life on Request and Assisted Suicide (Review Procedures) Act of Netherlands 2002

¹⁴ Alliance Vita; 'Euthanasia in the Netherlands' (November 2017) available at a <<https://www.alliancevita.org/en/2017/11/euthanasia-in-the-netherlands>> accessed 14 May 2025.

¹⁵ *Ibid*.

¹⁶ Netherlands jurisprudence (NJ) (1985) No 106, 451.

¹⁷ Akhigbe Agbonmeire, An Analysis of the Concept of Euthanasia in Relation to Right to Life in Nigeria (26 August, 2016) available at <SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3527310>> accessed 14 May 2025.

after other options have been considered and found wanting; the procedure must be performed by a physician; The physician must consult with an independent physician colleague who has experience in this field.¹⁸

There are various explanations surrounding the concept of right to die due to its diverse nature. However, owing to the complexity of the right to die, there are different theories that can adequately explain reasons that will push terminally ill patients to voluntarily request for death, in the process, the law of the state usually interferes in the personal affairs of the citizens to prevent them from doing what they desire to achieve.¹⁹ It is imperative to understand the nature and some theories surrounding the right to die in order to provide adequate and appropriate policies that can regulate the request for death by the terminally ill patients. Hence, this research work will examine the jurisprudential thoughts and perspectives from theories of social contract, utilitarianism and humanism to determine whether this may provide a consistent standard for resolving the fundamental issues on the right to die.

2.0 Jurisprudential schools of thought

The concept of right to die is not applicable in all jurisdictions and there are various explanations or justifications surrounding this concept because of its diverse nature. However, due to the complexity of the right to die, there are some theories for instances, Humanism Theory and Utilitarianism Theory, that can explain the motivational factors that would make a terminally ill patient who is going through excruciating pains to request for death. It is also imperative and pertinent to understand the nature and reasons the Humanism Theory and Utilitarianism Theory support the right to die in order to provide adequate and appropriate policies that can regulate the request for death by the terminally ill patients who are experiencing severe pain. But in the process, the Social Contract theory would shed light on the reason law of the state usually interferes in the personal affairs of the citizens to prevent them from doing what they desire to achieve.

2.1 Social Contract Theory on the Right to Die

The right to die is not a universally applicable concept. This is because each sovereign state decides or determines the legality of the right to die. The divergence in the laws in operation in various states contributed to the complexity of the right to die.²⁰ One can be of the opinion that what is the concern of the state if an individual wants to exercise the right to die as same is believed to be a personal decision which should not require any duty to seek the consent of any authority to do it. From the view point of the right to die, the use of the word right could be perceived as something given or entrusted which the receiver is qualified to possess.²¹ Hence, the only institution which has the power to arrogate certain rights is the state²² but how does the state get involved in the personal affairs of human being? It is on this note that social contract theory will be examined in order to comprehend the relationship between the rights of an individual including the right to die and the position of the state in terms of regulation.

Generally, social contract theory has different philosophical explanations from various scholars. There are a few numbers of exponents on the social contract theory but amongst the exponents are the major ones who are; Thomas Hobbes, John Lock and Jean Jack Pousseau. But later, Immanuel Kant, Herbert Spancer, John Rawls, Robert Nozick and host of others elaborated on the theory.²³ The state of nature in social contract theory refers to a hypothetical pre-political condition where there is no government or established social order. This state is characterized by individuals acting in their own self-interest, without

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ Musa Muhammad and Titus Monday, 'Social Contract Theories of Hobbes, Locke and Rousseau: An Extrapolation of Point of Harmony and Tensions' 2020 2(4) *Educational Resurgence Journal* 124-125.

²⁰ Peter Singer, 'Unsanctifying Human Life: Essays On Ethics' In John Ladd, *Ethical Issues Relating To Life And Death* (New York: Oxford University Press , 1979) p. 215

²¹ *Ibid*

²² *Ibid*

²³ Musa Muhammad and Titus Monday, 'Social Contract Theories of Hobbes, Locke and Rousseau: An Extrapolation of Point of Harmony and Tensions' 2020 2(4) *Educational Resurgence Journal* 124-125.

any constraints of law or morality.²⁴ Social contract theory suggests that individuals voluntarily agree to give up some of their natural freedoms in exchange for the protection and benefits of a government, thus moving from the state of nature to a more organized society.²⁵ The voluntary agreement between men through a social contract theory to form a state raises the following questions; what was the situation of men before the existence of the state? What are the terms of the agreement created in respect of the formation of the state? Between the state and the individuals, who is the superior? The response provided in respect to the first question, man was in the state of nature before the creation of the state while the last two questions are centred on the nature of the contract entered into and the attribute of the sovereignty.²⁶ In other words, there is no established authority or system of law to regulate behavior in the state of nature, individuals are free to do as they please, with no enforcement mechanisms to prevent them from harming others or violating their rights. Because individuals act in their own self-interest and there are no rules or laws to prevent it, the state of nature is often characterized by competition, conflict, and even war. As described by Thomas Hobbes, life in the state of nature is often depicted as "solitary, poor, nasty, brutish, and short" due to the lack of security, protection, and the constant threat of violence.²⁷ The social contract theory argues that individuals rationally recognize the disadvantages of the state of nature and choose to agree to a social contract, giving up some of their natural freedom in exchange for the protection and benefits of a government and legal system.²⁸ This was as a result of certain in-born characters of man some of which are; self-centeredness of men, perpetual and ceaseless struggle of control, equality of need, scarcity of resources, equality of human power, clashes of appetites, desire to gain control and limited altruism led to the action and reaction of men in the state of nature without law and justice and a result, Hobbes described the state of nature summarily as solitary, nasty, barbaric, brutish and short.²⁹ Hobbes was of the view that during the state of nature, the rich are the mighty, there was no room for industry or education as man lived solitary live style and this promote the natural power of men to oppress others.³⁰ Hobbes³¹ believed the state of nature was a war of all against all, characterized by constant conflict and fear of death. He argued that the social contract is necessary to establish a sovereign power to enforce laws and maintain order. Locke³² envisioned a state of nature where individuals have natural rights (life, liberty, and property) and are bound by the law of nature. He argued that the social contract is formed to protect these natural rights and prevent their violation. While Rousseau³³ saw the state of nature as a state of freedom and equality, where individuals are self-sufficient and not dependent on

²⁴ Ibid

²⁵ Ibid

²⁶ Andre Munro, 'State of nature' available at <<https://www.britannica.com/topic/state-of-nature-political-theory>> accessed 14 May 2025

²⁷ Ibid

²⁸ Musa Muhammad and Titus Monday, 'Social Contract Theories of Hobbes, Locke and Rousseau: An Extrapolation of Point of Harmony and Tensions' 2020 2(4) *Educational Resurgence Journal* 124-125.

²⁹ Big-Alabo Sotonye, 'Hobbesian Conception of Human Nature: Moral Implications for Nigeria Society' 2019 6(6) *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation (IJRSI)* 53

See also, Daniel Weltman, 'Nasty, Brutish, and Short': Thomas Hobbes on Life in the State of Nature', 2021, available at <<https://1000wordphilosophy.com/2021/07/14/hobbes-on-the-state-of-nature/>> Accessed 10 May 2025

³⁰ Ibid

³¹ Thomas Hobbes (5 April 1588 – 4 December 1679) was an English [philosopher](#), best known for his 1651 book [Leviathan](#), in which he expounds an influential formulation of [social contract](#) theory. He is considered to be one of the founders of modern [political philosophy](#).

³² John Locke (29 August 1632–28 October 1704) was an English philosopher and physician, widely regarded as one of the most influential of [the Enlightenment](#) thinkers and commonly known as the father of [liberalism](#). Considered one of the first of the British [empiricists](#) and is equally important to [social contract](#) theory.

³³ Jean-Jacques Rousseau (28 June 1712–2 July 1778) was a [Genevan](#) philosopher), writer, and composer. His [political philosophy](#) influenced the progress of the [Age of Enlightenment](#) throughout Europe, as well as aspects of the [French Revolution](#) and the development of modern political, economic, and educational thought.

others. He believed the social contract is necessary to create a society that is based on the general will and protects the freedom of all citizens.³⁴

Despite the little difference in the opinions of these three exponents, it can be pointed out that their explanations on the state of nature espoused the situation of fear of chaos created by men against one another at different levels. It was believed that the best solution to the challenges of the state of nature was to establish a mutual agreement that involves two factors which are; the agreement not to harm one another and the promise to keep the agreement with one another. The agreement was the beginning of the social contract which came with a price of submitting the liberties or rights of men in order to secure stable social contract.³⁵

The idea of social contract led to the creation of a central authority that is believed to be very strong capable enough to enforce the rules agreed upon by the people and to provide protection of lives, properties and certain extent of liberty with adequate security. As a result, it led to the abandonment of rights of men and confer the rights on the impartial authority of the state with the view of getting protection from the constituted authority who shall rule them under the common laws, and create enforcement mechanisms for the social contract agreement entered into between the entity called the state and individuals.³⁶

As much as the social contract theory helped to solve the problem experienced during the state of nature, it has few challenges and one of them is non-participation of every member of the society in the decision made.³⁷ This challenge is one of the current issues in Nigerian legal system which encourages few selected people to dictate the affairs of every man without proper consultation from the citizens or those who are directly affected by the laws, orders made and by extension to the prohibitions of certain acts in medical parlance such as the right to die. In addition, social contract theory has also been contradicted on the ground that it was calculated for political speculations, favouritism, bad laws, bad philosophy, unhistorical and a mere fiction created by philosophers and exponents of the theory.³⁸

The actions and inactions of men during state of nature as mentioned above led to the formation of a single contract between the men and the state in which the men of the society abandoned their rights under the states of nature and submit them to the established society, the state and the government for the purpose of providing adequate security for them. The formation of this contract led to social contract theory in which the state as the government was established to regulate the conducts and the affairs of men. The establishment of the state brought about the communalization of men and powers, establishment of legislative, agreement on taxation and other institutions.³⁹

However, the contract made people to relinquish their rights, capacity and power for collective purposes. The power given to the state could not be withdrawn because of the fear of returning to the state of nature which is characterized with anarchy, violence and in security. This was how the state became so powerful and exercise absolute sovereignty and constitutional government which controls the natural liberty of men. Although, according to Locke, the right relinquished by the people was not absolute as there are some rights that are fundamental which cannot be given up by men, some of these rights are right to life, liberty and property which must be kept intact and this further placed the society in the position to retain the authority of the state. Flowing from above, the controversy on the right to die was as a result of the existing legislations made by the state for men which are in force and in conflict with the right of liberty

³⁴ Musa Muhammad and Titus Monday, 'Social Contract Theories of Hobbes, Locke and Rousseau: An Extrapolation of Point of Harmony and Tensions' 2020 2(4) *Educational Resurgence Journal* 128.

³⁵ Kevin J Browne, 'Introduction to the Social Contract Theory available online at <<https://docplayer.net/20908323-Introduction-to-the-social-contract-theory-1.html>> Accessed 14 May 2025

³⁶ Andre Munro, 'State of nature' available at <<https://www.britannica.com/topic/state-of-nature-political-theory>> accessed 14 May 2025

³⁷ Big-Alabo Sotonye, 'Hobbesian Conception of Human Nature: Moral Implications for Nigeria Society' 2019 6(6) *International Journal of Research and Scientific Innovation (IJRSI)* 53

³⁸ Musa Muhammad and Titus Monday, 'Social Contract Theories of Hobbes, Locke and Rousseau: An Extrapolation of Point of Harmony and Tensions' 2020 2(4) *Educational Resurgence Journal* 126

³⁹ Ibid

inherent in men. Because the state is now in the position to control men, the issue of the right to die becomes a matter of the state because the state is in charge of the rights allowed under the constitution. Furthermore, social contract brought about the appealing justification of its usefulness in terms of international Treaties and also in the alienation of power to the International Criminal Court and even the United Nation in order to reconcile the power of the state with the freedom and equality of each associate.⁴⁰ Sequel to this, International laws and regulations on various acts including the right to die under the medical law derived its source from the components of the social contract theory.

2.2 Utilitarianism theory on the Right to Die

One of the major arguments in support of the right to die is the patient autonomy. The divergence in the interpretation of patient autonomy in various states contributed to the complexity of the right to die. Some philosophers believed that the right to die of a patient suffering from terminal ailment should be within the personal decision of a patient especially with such terminal sickness. Hence, a patient who is terminally ill should be able to determine his own happiness and how he wants to end his own life in the face of agony and excruciating pains. In essence the request of a dying patient should be granted, even where such request will lead to death as long as it brings maximum happiness to the patient and larger number of people.⁴¹ Thus, an action will be considered as morally right when it contributes to the maximum achievement of the good will and happiness enjoyed by maximum number of people.

One of the main exponents of this theory is Jeremy Bentham.⁴² In this theory, happiness is perceived from hedonistic notion in order to calculate the worth of pleasures. This is done by calculating the sum of total pleasure and pain in order to justify the consequence of an action. According to Bentham, to achieve and promote pleasure and avoid pain is more important in human nature and as such the maximum utility of happiness of the greatest number of people should determine what is obtainable and morally justified in the society. The well-being of the people in the society is determined by the calculation of pains and pleasure they experience. Thus, utilitarianism theory promotes happiness, pleasure, knowledge, friendship and autonomy of the people as long as it is beneficial to mankind and also creates maximum happiness for the greatest number of people.⁴³ If a terminally ill person is able to escape prolong painful death and allowed to be administered the lethal dosage of the drug, others involved in the treatment would benefit, since the consequence will bring about the greatest balance of good and evil.⁴⁴ And under no circumstance can such assistance rendered to assist a terminally ill patient at his request can be morally equivalent to murder.⁴⁵

Most times, some patients are going through life threatening ailments which as a result will propel them to request for death due to futile treatment procedure and unbearable pains such patients are experiencing. Thus utilitarian theory promotes painless experience for humanity.⁴⁶ According to this theory, for instance, if a person is terminally ill, he is in stage four of blood cancer and because of his chemotherapies, such a person is enduring severe pains along with his family members who are responsible for his care. In a situation like this, if such person wants to end his life by requesting that he should be accorded the right to die, according to the utilitarian, his action will be morally justified. This is because it will create happiness for maximum number of people that is, the terminally ill patient will be saved from anguish and pains, the family will be relieved from worries associated with monetary, medication, medical treatment and the hospital as well will benefit by freeing some rooms for other patients to use, have attention for other viable patients and finally the patient will enjoy a quality life.

⁴⁰ Jason Neidleman, 'The Social Contract Theory in a Global Context' page 2 (9 October 2012), available at <https://www.e-ir.info/2012/10/09/the-social-contract-theory-in-a-global-context/> Accessed 14 May 2025.

⁴¹ Matti Häyry, 'Just Better Utilitarianism' (2020) 30(2) *Cambridge Quarterly of Healthcare Ethics* 6-7.

⁴² He was an English philosopher, economist, and theoretical jurist, the earliest and chief expounder of utilitarianism. He was born on February 15, 1748 London, England.

⁴³ Matti Häyry, 'Just Better Utilitarianism' (2020) 30(2) *Cambridge Quarterly of Healthcare Ethics* 6-7.

⁴⁴ Madeline Jordan, 'The Ethical Considerations of Physician-assisted Suicide' (2017) 4 *Physician-assisted Suicide* 2-3.

⁴⁵ Marina Budić, 'Suicide, Euthanasia and the Duty to Die: A Kantian Approach to Euthanasia' (2017) 29 *Philosophy and Society*, 91.

⁴⁶ Ibid

With this, many people would have benefited from the patient's action and thus it is morally justified. Furthermore, this theory is concerned with the measurement of pain and pleasure to determine the action to take, thus, where the intensity of the torment and its duration will prolong the pains of a patient, cause loss of pride, agony and uncertainty of recovery, such a patient should be accorded the right to die and allowed to go to create room for happiness.

This theory is related to situational ethics and as postulated by Joseph Fletcher,⁴⁷ the decision making of a person should be based on the current situation the person is facing and not based on the law.⁴⁸ This theory perceived that it is unjustified when people say rules must not be broken when they are in difficult situation. This is because where there is too much strict application of the law; it means the more importance is placed on the law than the life of a human being. People must obey the rules, duties and obligation placed by the religion and the state, however, a person must also be given a choice to make his own decision based on the situation he finds himself especially in a difficult situation. This theory stipulates that people should be considered first before the rules and the principles of the state. Utilitarian theory posited that each individual case should be treated on its own merit and the calculation of pain and pleasure should determine what should be done. Thus, utilitarian theory will support the right to die if the consequence of such action will primarily add to the happiness of the patient, create a balance between pain and pleasure and have a wider positive impact on the doctors, hospitals, nurses, relations, law and the public as a whole.

2.3 The Humanism Theory on the Right to Die

Humanists are a common term used to describe the proponents or advocates of this school. They are not religious but adhere to moral standards derived from human reason. They base their values on following the law and showing respect for others unless doing so is considered cruel or endangers the life of a person.⁴⁹ The quality of life and respect for personal autonomy are seen as important areas of interest for this school of thought to bolster their claims that right to die voluntarily is morally right. The protagonists contend that everyone should have the option to pass away painlessly and respectfully if they are suffering from uncontrollable agony or the irreversible loss of things that give life meaning. As a result, the humanist school of thought maintain, that by refusing to accord the patient the right to die; no significant benefits or improvements would be achieved.⁵⁰

The humanists generally support the concept of right to die, but insist that certain obligations and measures should be put in place, such as counselling and the involvement of other physicians for second opinion prior to the procedure and also to ensure that the persistent request by the patient to terminate his life is absolutely voluntary.⁵¹ In essence, the humanist school of thought opposes and rejects involuntary termination of life.⁵²

3.0 RECOMMENDATIONS

Despite the position of social contract theory, it is apparent from jurisprudential thoughts and perspectives on humanism and utilitarianism discussed above, that every person is worthy and deserving of respect even in sickness and death. In essence, patient has a right to live with dignity and as such, he should have a right to die with dignity. Flowing from this, it is recommended as follows:

⁴⁷ He was an American professor who founded the theory of situational ethics in the 1960s, and was a pioneer in the field of bioethics. He was born in April 10, 1905 and died in October 28, 1991.

⁴⁸ Ali Khan, Bisma Khan and Javeria Din, 'Dilemma of Euthanasia Is Morally Justified or Not in the Light of Theories' (2017) *Addiction Research* 1, 2017, 3.

⁴⁹ Matt Lamb, 'Pro-life Means Opposing Euthanasia, Assisted Suicide' available at <<http://studentsforlife.org>> accessed 24 February, 2025.

⁵⁰ Y. Olomjobi, *Medical and Health Law: The Right to Health* (Ikeja: Princeton Press Ltd, 2019) 366

⁵¹ Ibid

⁵² Humanist Perspective Euthanasia (March 2016) available at <<https://understandinghumanism.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/Euthanasia-humanist-perspective.pdf>> accessed 15 May 2025

1. That patient who is terminally ill, suffering from incurable disease, helpless and experiencing excruciating pain or is certified to be medically dead should be accorded right to die voluntarily without any form of coercion or force
2. That the right to die voluntarily should be vested in a competent adult (18 years and above) who is experiencing or suffering severe or intolerable distress (not necessarily physical) from an incurable illness, to receive medical help to die at his or her considered and persistent request. This implies that such patient specifically requests for termination of his life. In this instance, there should be no prospect for improvement. The decision to terminate the life of the patient must be one of last resort, after considering whether there is any less drastic alternative.
3. That a comprehensive and specific legal framework should be designed which outlines the nature and definition of concept of right to die, the conditions under which the right to die would be permitted or accorded and carried out, the process for requesting for right to die, the role of healthcare providers, and the safeguards to prevent abuse.
4. The legal framework should incorporate certain obligations, conditions and measures such as counselling and the involvement of other independent physicians. such persons must be capable of making that decision and determined by an expert to be so capable and another independent physicians who have a wealth of experience in the field for second opinion prior to the procedure and also to ensure that the persistent request by the patient to terminate his life is absolutely voluntary; consent must be obtained from such patient both verbally and in writing, witnessed by at least two people to be specified and certified by two competent medical practitioners; such person must be suffering from an acute, terminal illness which cannot be relieved; such procedure must only be carried out by a certified physician and such other requirements as necessary to prevent abuse. Such legal framework should describe in detail what excruciating pains and terminal diseases are and when a person might be deemed to be terminally ill; options available to a medical practitioner when dealing with a patient who refuses medical treatment; definition of consent and who can give consent; the available alternatives for a medical practitioner when there is no representation of the terminally sick patient, sanctions for persons whether physicians or individuals who abuse the guidelines set up in the legislation etc.
5. There should be awareness on the concept of right to die in Nigeria, ensuring that there is ample sensitization of people on the true meaning of the concept, paying attention to the importance of performing the procedure. This could be done by initiating comprehensive public education campaigns to inform citizens about the concept of right to die and its ethical, moral, and social implications in Nigeria. This should include discussions in communities, medical facilities (hospitals), schools, religious institutions, and the media.
6. The specific legislation on the concept of right to die must bring the position of the law in Nigeria in line with best medical and acceptable practices, in order to enable doctors to act in the best interests of their patients without any form of fear of prosecution or the need to dissemble.
7. The specific legislation put in place should allow for the use of advanced directives by terminally ill patients. This could be done either by patients acquiring and wearing a medallion which signifies that the wearer does not wish to be resuscitated in a medical emergency. This medallion would be engraved with the wearer's name, date of birth, signature, and portrait, meeting all of the regulatory requirements for an advanced directive or by allowing authorized hospitals to attach a DNR slip to the file of any terminally ill patient to ensure that no extreme measures are used on such persons.
8. There should be established mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating the implementation of laws and policies on right to die in order to assess their impact on patients, families, healthcare providers, and society as a whole. This should include chances for feedback and improvement, reporting requirements, and routine case reviews.

4.0 CONCLUSION

The concept of right to die debate involves complex ethical considerations, including questions about the sanctity of life and the role of medical professionals. It has received serious attention in the medico-legal field and among clinicians, researchers, sovereign states, governmental and non-governmental organizations, policy and decision makers, religious bodies and society at large. The concept of the right to die is one of the most controversial aspects amongst other rights of an individual and limitation placed on such rights by the state authorities as discussed under the social contract theory. Patients opt for death as a result of many reasons ranging from persistent organ failure and terminal ailments. In spite of the fact that the concept of right to die is unknown under Nigerian Legal System and in advocating for the change in the law, it is imperative and pertinent to state in particular, the concept of personal autonomy and freedom of choice, inherent in that concept, for an individual to waive the right to his own life. Thus, right to die voluntarily, if vested in the people that are dying or at vegetative stage, suffering from excruciating pain or endless distress caused by incurable or terminal ailment, it will definitely put an end to prolonged suffering which can diminish human dignity and unbearable pain which is a form of dehumanization, therefore individuals would have the right to make decisions about their own bodies and lives. This will bring the position of the law in Nigeria in line with best medical and acceptable practices in other jurisdictions, in order to enable doctors to act in the best interests of their patients without any form of fear of prosecution or the need to dissemble.